

Sustainable Best Practices and External Environmental Factors as Determinants of Hotel Performance in Region XI

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Abstract: Nowadays, sustainable best practices are given more importance globally with higher expectations now centered in the tourism industry. It is with this that this study aimed to determine the sustainable best practices and environmental factors as determinants of hotel performance in Region XI. Specifically, it examined the relationship between sustainable best practices and external environmental factors to hotel performance and its influence to each other. This study used descriptive-correlational research design with 400 hotel employees as respondents. Three sets of survey questionnaires were used to obtain information from the participants. Pearson *r* and regression analysis were used to analyze the data. The findings revealed that the sustainable business practices are often evident and the role external environmental factors are always evident. Moreover, the hotel performance is outstanding. Finally, sustainable best practices and external environmental factor are significant determinants of hotel performance.

Keywords: Business Management, Sustainable Best Practices, External Environmental Factors, Hotel Performance, Descriptive – Correlational, Philippines

I. Introduction

Sustainable practices are given more importance globally with higher expectations. Most of its efforts are centered in the tourism industry since its processes and services may impact the environment which in return contributes to water pollution, global warming and depletion of energy supply (Sloan et al. 2009; Klepsch & Schneider, 2012). Although, several hotels around the globe adapted sustainable practices they are still a minority compared to the growing number of hotels who don't. In addition, Akrofi (2016) said that the external environmental factors have a continuing impact to the performance of hotels worldwide. Despite years of conservation efforts, hotels' energy and resource use is still considerable—but that also opens the way to further sustainability efforts, which have the double benefit of saving money and benefiting the environment (Aznar, 2016).

In 2017, United Nations considered the hotel industry as the most flourished tourism development: change in policies, business practices and consumer towards a more sustainable tourism sector that can contribute to the sustainable development goal (UNWTO, 2017). Moreover, Faitag (2018) article said that the performance of hotels is decreasing every year. However, this contradicts DDI Development (2018) claimed that it is the growing industry in the world because of its sustainable practices. Relatively, Philippine government includes the hotel industry in its development plan and pointed out that hoteliers must put into consideration sustainable practices to survive in the industry. In the same manner, Davao region's development which is centered on the tourism sector, including the different hotel industry in this region faces problems and issues on sustainability especially on the consumption of large amounts of natural water and energy which also leave behind substantial amount of waste in the place. Recently, Manila Bay has been closed for some time to the public for rehabilitation; toxic waste has been rampant which caused damaging effect to it, hotels and establishments nearby had made attributing factors to this damage. This also happened to the popular summer destination in Aklan, the Boracay Island: was also closed for reclamation as the flourishing of the hotels and restobars in the island caused environmental damage to its natural resources. These closures affected the performance of the hotels as some loses its clients which also caused the decrease of their income.

Consequently, there has been growing social concern and demands among different stakeholders for environmentally friendly hotels. DATA recognizes and accredits hotels that have remarkable performance in terms of its services. Performances of these hotels are regularly assessed based on its conformation to sustainable practices and using the PESTLE analysis. Despite the growing demand and popularity, only a handful of hotel companies are said to have adopted environmental management and used it for gaining competitive advantage, Padilla (2012).

In addition, the researcher has difficulty on finding literature that discussed the relationship of the three variables. Instead, only literature that shows bivariate relationship of sustainable best practices and hotel performance; and external environmental factor and hotel performance relationship variables. It is for this reason that the researchers were inspired to determine if sustainable best practices and external environmental factors are determinants of hotel performance.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to determine the sustainable business practices and environmental factor as determinants of hotel performance in Region XI. Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

1.1.1. What is the level of sustainable best practices in Region XI in terms of:

1.1.1.1 Commitment and Awareness

1.1.1.2 Energy Efficiency

1.1.1.3 Solid Waste Minimization

1.1.1.4 Air and Water Quality

1.1.1.5 Water Conservation

1.1.1.6 Environmental Purchasing

1.1.2. What is the level of external environmental factors of hotel industry in terms of?

1.1.2.1 Political Environmental Factor

1.1.2.2 Economic Environmental Factor

1.1.2.3 Technological Environmental Factor

1.1.2.4 Legal Environmental Factor

1.1.3. What is the level of hotel performance in terms of?

1.1.3.1 Financial Performance

1.1.3.2 Competitiveness

1.1.3.3 Employee Performance

1.1.3.4 Operational Efficiency

1.1.3.5 Operational Efficiency

1.1.3.6 Innovativeness

1.1.3.7 Service Quality

1.1.4. Is there a significant relationship between sustainable best practices and external environmental factor to hotel performance?

1.1.5. What is the combined and singular influence of sustainable best practices and external environmental factors on hotel performance?

1.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Brundtland (1987) report on the Coalition of Environmentally Responsible Economies or known as (CERES) which is focused on the sustainable business practices and external environmental factors that affects the performance of hotel industry in the world. With this it is theorized that in the hospitality company it is important to train and educate their staff about the necessary environmental sustainability practices (Chen, Legrand & Sloan. 2009).

The second and third variable, external environmental factor is anchored on the PESTLE analysis theory of PESTEL by Adamski (2017) which espoused that the best way to measure the performance of the hotel industry is to use modern ways to find the factors that affect it.

This is also supported with the theory on strategic practice whereby external business practices has a big impact on the environmental factors on the organizations strategic positions; as Johnson et al.,(2008) identified the key components of external business environment which is made up of macro external factors, industry factors, competitors and markets (Akrofi, 2016).

1.3 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework, showing the relationship between the variables of this study. Mainly, the framework shows the relationship between the predictor variable and the outcome variable. The first independent variable is sustainable business practices with its indicators commitment and awareness, energy efficiency, solid waste minimization, air and water quality, water conservation, and environmental purchasing (Bartkeviciute&Puchkova, 2013).

The second independent variable, external environment factors with its indicators political environmental factors, economic environmental factors, technological environmental factors and legal environmental factors (Zhang, 2016).

Furthermore, the indicators for hotel performance as the dependent variable are financial performance, competitiveness, employee performance, operational efficiency, innovativeness and service quality (Kala & Bagri, 2014).

INDEPENDENT VARIABLE

DEPENDENT VARIABLE

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Showing the Relationship of the Variables of the Study

II. Methods

2.1 Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlation technique to investigate the sustainable business practices and environmental factor as determinants of hotel performance in Region XI. Descriptive research design provided an accurate picture of the status or characteristics of a situation or phenomena and it focuses on describing the variables that exist in a given situation. On the other hand, correlation research determined the relationship and influence of Sustainable business practices and External Environmental Factors with Hotel performance, thus this determined strength of a relationship between variables and how well the two variables were correlated (Creswell, 2003).

This study was mainly focused on identifying the relationship of the best sustainable practices of hotels, external environmental factors and hotel performance.

2.2 Research Locale

The study was conducted in the (40) DOT (Department of Tourism) accredited hotels and inns in Region XI since it was within the proximity and network of the researcher. Distributing 10 Questionnaires per hotel, a total of 400 respondents

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who were regular employees with 3 years' experience were gathered. The possibility for the general applicability of the findings was limited by the scope and the sample.

Presented figure 2 was the map of the Philippines consisting of 17 regions where Region XI was located in the Island of Mindanao. Davao Region, was formerly called Southern Mindanao (Cebuano: Habagatang Mindanao; Filipino: Timog Mindanao), was an administrative region in the Philippines, designated as Region XI. It was situated at the southeastern portion of Mindanao, comprising of five provinces: [Compostela Valley](#), [Davao del Norte](#), [Davao del Sur](#), [Davao Oriental](#) and [Davao Occidental](#), the newly created province.

Davao Region is the most populous region in Mindanao and the 7th most populous in the country, with a total of 4,893,318 inhabitants in 2015. Davao City, its regional capital, was also the largest city in Mindanao, with an area of 2,444 km², the largest in the country and one of the largest in the world, and has 1,632,991 inhabitants in 2015, making it the fourth most populous city in the country and the most populous city proper in the entire [Visayas](#)-Mindanao region. The respondents were located in Davao City.

Figure 2. Map of the Philippines and Region XI

2.3 Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the employees of the 40 DOT accredited Hotels and inns in Region XI. In particular, the respondents were those regular employees in the different hotels who were included as the respondents of the study. However, hotels and inns in those areas which were critical will be excluded in the study.

The 400 respondents were chosen using purposive sampling, following the criteria that they had to be regular employees with 3 years of working experience. Distributing 10 questionnaires per hotel helped the researcher in obtaining a total number of 400 respondents. This technique was used following Kulshrestha (2013), who espoused that purposive sampling is appropriate for selecting samples based on specific criteria.

2.4 Research Instrument

This study used three sets of adopted questionnaires: part one was sustainable business practices, part two was for the external environment factors and part three was for the hotel performance in Region XI.

The first set of questionnaires on sustainable business practices was adopted from the final report on sustainable tourism indicators and destination management by CERES (2001). It had 6 indicators for sustainable best practice namely commitment and awareness, energy efficiency, solid waste minimization, air and water quality, water conservation, environmental purchasing.

The second set of the instrument embarked with the external environment factors of hotels employees. It is composed of 4 indicators namely: political environmental factor, economic environmental factor, technological environmental factor and legal environmental factor as mentioned by Akrofi (2016).

The third part/set of the instrument boarded with the hotel performance. This was composed of six indicators namely: financial performance, competitiveness, employee performance, operational efficiency, innovativeness, service quality as mentioned by Kala & Bagri (2014).

The researchers subjected the questionnaire to validation by the different expert evaluator's and after it was validated this was subjected for pilot test to get the reliability of the questions.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

After receiving the approved letter of endorsement sought from Dean of the Graduate School, the researcher made another letter to all heads of hotels in Region XI asking permission to allow the researcher to conduct the study in their respective agencies and offices. Likewise, the researcher asked approval for the distribution of survey questionnaire to their respective employees. The researcher personally handed in the questionnaire to the respective respondents. Given the time frame of two weeks the researcher retrieved the entire questionnaire and tabulated the data gathered from the respondents and sent it to the assigned statistician through email which was then subjected to statistical analysis.

After the receipt of the statistical result, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the data. Finally, conclusion was drawn from the findings of the study and recommendation was formulated based on the conclusions of the study.

2.5 Statistical Treatment

Mean and standard deviation was used to determine the central tendency and the dispersion of the data. On the other hand, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the linear relationship between sustainable best practices, external environmental factors and hotel performance.

Regression Analysis was also used to determine the beta coefficients of the interrelationship of the three variables as input to mediation analysis.

2.6 Ethical Consideration

This research was submitted to the UIC-REC for the full board review of the ethical aspects of the investigation. The ethical review was anchored on Belmont Report 1979 strictly adhering to the principles, in respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. Specifically, this research was subjected to evaluation of the UIC-REC as regards to the 10 dimensions of research ethics that include social value, informed consent, vulnerability issues, risks-benefit ration, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, qualification of the researchers, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement.

Ethical consideration was considered as one of the most important parts of the research. The research participants should be free from any harm; the dignity of the research participants should be respected and be respected and should be given top priority; the full consent from the participants had been secured before conducting the survey; the privacy of research participants had to be safeguarded; high level of confidentiality on research data was maintained; secrecy on the whereabouts of individuals and organizations participating in the research had been guaranteed; had refrained from any deception or exaggeration regarding the aims and objectives of the study; affiliations in any forms, sourcing of funds, as well as any possible conflicts of interest had to be declared; any type of communication in relation to the research had been done with utmost honesty and transparency; and any type of misleading information had been avoided, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased manner had been eradicated.

III. Results and Discussion

3.1 Level of Sustainable Best Practices

Presented in the Table is the level of sustainable best practices of hotel employees in Region XI. Sustainable best practices contained six components, namely commitment and awareness, energy efficiency, solid waste minimization, air and water quality, water conservation and environmental purchasing. According to Honey (2008) as the understanding of the need to protect the environment for future generations, sustainability practices are now given more importance in the hotel industry.

The level of sustainable best practices of hotel employees has an overall mean score of 4.12 or High. This result implies that the sustainable practices are often manifested. It is also revealed that *commitment and awareness* got the highest category mean of 4.25 described as Very High while *environmental purchasing* got the lowest category mean of 4.03 or High. The rest of the indicators got category means ranging from 4.09 to 4.15 all described as High.

Table 1: Level of Sustainable Best Practices of Hotel Employees in Region XI

Item	Indicators	SD	Mean	Description
1	Commitment and Awareness	.58	4.25	Very High
2	Energy Efficiency	.58	4.12	High
3	Solid Waste Minimization	.75	4.13	High
4	Air and Water Quality	.72	4.15	High
5	Water Conservation	.71	4.09	High
6	Environmental Purchasing	.72	4.03	High
	Overall Mean	.53	4.12	High

This result conforms to the statement of Prud'homme and Raymond (2013) that customers' attitudes towards more responsible best sustainable practices depend on how they behave and how important it is in their daily life to take responsible decisions in terms of caring for the environment. Also, it supports the observation of Bader, (2005); Dickson, (2010); & Aznar (2016) that hotels' dedication to sustainable practices attracts more customers, builds a better reputation, and generates more economic investment, reducing the negative consequences associated with the massive concentration of tourists in some locations.

This result also conforms to the study of McAllister (2014) on solid waste management in hotels who affirms that minimizing waste necessitates reducing the amount of waste generated from the business sector and society must transform its patterns associated to production, consumption and reforming products to eliminate the accumulation of more waste.

Furthermore, the result is congruent to the study of Rahman, et al. (2014) in terms of sustainable practices on maintaining the quality of air and water and conserving water consumption. These studies all confirmed that these aspects of sustainable practices are high in hotels and collaboration with government agencies should also be considered in all phases of land use management and planning. The developers should adapt sustainable practices in their projects including conservation of water consumption. Likewise, the purchasing practices of hotel management have significantly affected the environment and hotel industry which examined the importance of considering environmental factors in purchasing of any products or services in the hotel industry (Carter, Kale and Grimm, 2000).

3.2 Level of External Environmental Factors

Data in Table 2 elucidated the level of external environmental factors of hotel employees in region XI. The external environmental factors are confined to four mechanisms, namely *political environmental factors, economic environmental factors, technological environmental factors and legal environmental factors.*

It is revealed in Table 2 that the level of external environmental factors has an overall mean score of 4.34 or Very High, which means that external environmental factors are always evident in the hotel industry in Region XI. The *legal environmental factors* got the highest category mean score of 4.46 or Very High. This means that the role of legal environment factors is always evident. The result is consistent with Brundtland (2017) confirmation that the legal environment is necessary for the growth and development of the hotel industry. This factor includes safety and health laws. It also conforms to the study of Chou (2014) who states that people only get attracted to leisure hotels that are legal and can provide secure services.

Table 2: Level of External Environmental Factors of Hotel Employees in Region XI

Item	Indicators	SD	Mean	Description
1	Political Environmental Factors	.70	4.28	Very High
2	Economic Environmental Factors	.64	4.28	Very High
3	Technological Environmental Factors	.61	4.34	Very High
4	Legal Environmental Factors	.62	4.46	Very High
	Overall Mean	.56	4.34	Very High

The technological environmental factor has a category mean of 4.34 or described as very high which indicates that the role of technological environment to the hotel industry is always manifested. This result aligns with the findings of Yoo, Sawyerr, & Tan (2015) that discovered that it is very important for companies especially the hotel industry to keep up to

date with these changes, not only because it will enable innovative new products, but will also give them a competitive advantage.

In addition, both political and economic environmental factors got a category mean of 4.28 described as very high, which indicates that the impact of the political and economic factors in the hotel industry is always manifested. This result is congruent to the study of Johnson, et al. (2008) who found that political and economic environmental factors can affect the operations of hotel industries as these agencies are expected to follow the law. Also, they pointed out that the main factors affecting the economic environment are economic, situation and factors such as energy prices, transport costs, the price of telecommunications services, quality standards, the influence of the banking sector and other sectors as well.

The current finding is also aligned to the study of Yunus, et al. (2014) who revealed that the hotel industry needs to take a pre-emptive approach and be ahead of these changes, rather than hurriedly making alterations to products and processed in a reactive way.

3.3 Level of Hotel Performance

The level of hotel performance in region XI is shown in Table 3. The hotel performance was determined through the six components, namely *financial performance, competitiveness, employee performance, operational efficiency, innovativeness and service quality*. The measurement of performance according Haktanir& Harris (2005) plays a vital role in planning and decision-making and connects strategic intent, competitive environment, income generation, service delivery process and calculated assessment.

Data reveal that hotel performance has an overall mean score of 4.21 or described as very high. This result implies that the hotel performance is outstanding meaning they have achieved beyond what is expected. It is also exhibited that *financial performance* and *competitiveness* have category means of 4.09 and 4.10 both described as high, while all the other indicators have category means ranging from 4.22 to 4.34 all described as very high. It can be gleaned reveals that among the indicators *operational efficiency* has the highest category mean of 4.34 or described as very high. This result implies that the hotels' performance in the aspect of operation is outstanding. It means that they are able to provide excellent service to their clients. Hence, they were able to develop loyal customers.

The result conforms to Aznar's (2016) study which stated that the sharing economy is a new phenomenon to uncountable consequences. It is a new form of economic activity affecting the way consumers make their decisions, forcing some traditional industries to rethink their strategies to survive in an environment where new substitutes by the sharing economy can affect negatively profitability and finally, governments have to rethink know to regulate this new form of activity.

Table 3: Level of Hotel Performance in Region XI

Item	Indicators	SD	Mean	Description
1	Financial Performance	.70	4.09	High
2	Competitiveness	.69	4.10	High
3	Employee Performance	.63	4.26	Very High
4	Operational Efficiency	.61	4.34	Very High
5	Innovativeness	.70	4.22	Very High
6	Service Quality	.67	4.23	Very High
	Overall Mean	.53	4.21	Very High

On the other hand, financial performance got the lowest category mean of 4.09 or high. This result means that sales growth is monitored monthly and annually. This finding corresponds to the study of Akrofi (2016) who asserted that organizations need to set clear goals and objectives, develop criteria for measurement of financial performance, evaluate and compare the financial performance against the goals and objectives of the organization to come up with a good financial plan.

In addition, the result also coincides with the studies of Edrogan and Baris (2017) who claimed that hotels should monitor and measure actual expenses against its operating costs to show how the hotel performed compared to a competitive set; Zhang (2016) who postulated that hotel employees are responsible for good customer relations and service. As such, hotel management is expected to compensate these efforts through a mutual motivation to decrease employee's turnover; Sintes and Mattson (2009) who disclosed that some of the employees of the company are innovative, full of initiative and provide suggestions to improve the performance of hotels where they are employed.

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Also, it confirms to the study of Wu & Ko (2013) who found that service quality is an indicator of the successful hotel industry and, thus, proper monitoring of all complaints and good feedbacks is necessary. Also, it jives with the finding of Wadongo, et al., (2010) who revealed that the key performance indicators of hotels include total revenue achieved, food, and beverage sales, total operating cost, total sales, customer satisfaction survey, relative market share, room occupancy and delivery speed flexibility.

3.4 Significance of the Relationship between variables

Table 4 presents the result of the correlation between the variables. Data shows that there is a significant relationship between sustainable business practices and hotel performance. It can be gleaned in the computed $r=.406$, $p<.05$. This means that the higher the sustainable business practices, the higher is the hotel performance.

Table 4: Correlation between measures

Paired Variables	r	P-value	Interpretation
Sustainable Business Practices and Hotel Performance	.406	.000	Significant
Sustainable Business Practices and External Environmental Factor	.467	.000	Significant
External Environmental Factor and Hotel Performance	.467	.000	Significant

Similarly, the relationship between sustainable best practices and environmental factor revealed a computed $r=.467$, $p<.05$ which is significant at $\alpha 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, this implies that a significant relationship exists between sustainable best practices and hotel performance. The result conforms to the finding of Bagur-Femenias et al., (2013) who found that the adoption of environmental practices improves the competitiveness of small travel agencies. Specifically, these authors found that the adoption of advanced environmental strategies allowed travel agencies to reduce operative cost and increase market share by differentiating themselves from the competitors.

In the same way, external environmental factors and hotel performance has a computed $r=.467$, $p<.05$. This result implies that environmental factor and hotel performance is found to be significant at $\alpha 0.05$ level of significance. This finding supports the theory on strategic practice of Johnson et al. (2008) whereby external sustainable practices have a big impact on the environmental factors on the organizations strategic positions which identified key components of external business environment which are made up of macro external factors, industry factors and competitors and markets (Akrofi, 2016).

However, this finding contradicts to Chong and Verma's (2013) insights on how an eco-certified hotel can affect hotel revenues, which revealed that no relationship exists between external environmental factors and hotel performance. The awareness and social pressure led the hotels to start managing the environmental impacts of their activities and to become accountable to society for this management. In this sense, Oliveira et al. (2016) warned that the interest of society in sustainability becomes a decisive factor for selecting a given tourism enterprise which represents a guarantee of comfort and hospitality.

3.5 Significance of the Influence of Sustainable Best Practices and Environmental Factors on Hotel Performance

The regression analysis was used to test the influence of sustainable business practices and environmental factors on hotel performance. The data reflected in Table 5 is the combined and singular influence of sustainable business practices and external environmental factors on hotel performance. Data shows that when the independent variables are interpreted individually, *external environmental factors* have the greatest influence on hotel performance as evident with its $p<.05$ and β coefficient of .346.

The r^2 of .280 indicates that 28% of the indicators of hotel performance can be attributed to the two independent variables. However, this also indicates that 72% of the variation in hotel performance is attributed to other variables not covered in the scope of the study.

The result conforms to the study of Claver-Cortés *et al.*, (2007) which disclosed that best sustainable practices and environmental factors greatly influenced hotel performance. This finding also conforms to Brundtland (1987) report on the Coalition of Environmentally Responsible Economies or known as (CERES) which focused on the effects of sustainable best practices and external environmental factors to the performance of hotel industry in the world. With this, it is theorized that the hospitality company should imperatively train and educate their staff about environmental sustainability practices (Chen, Legrand & Sloan. 2009).

Table 1: Combined and singular influence of sustainable best practices and environmental factors on hotel performance

Variables	Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Remarks
	Beta			
Best practices	.268	5.83	.00	Significant
Environmental factors	.366	7.96	.00	Significant

Note: R-square=.280, F=77.244, P<.05

IV. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were recommended. There is a significant relationship between sustainable best practices and external environmental factors as well as a significant relationship between external environmental factors and hotel performance of hotels in Region XI. Moreover, Sustainable best practices and external environmental factors are good determinants of hotel performance.

Since, most of the ratings of respondents in the sustainable best practices vary, there is a need to re-examine and enhance other indicators to improve their sustainable practices especially in terms of environmental factors. In this regard, hotel owners and managers may revisit their practices on the procurement of supplies that involves using papers with chlorine. They may provide periodic re-orientation seminars and training on sustainable practices among its employees. Though external environmental factors are all very high, still there is a need for the hotel management to look into the influence of political and economic factors which is relatively high.

Furthermore, With the relatively high performance on financial performance and competitiveness, hotel management may consider implementing strategies that may optimize the utilization of financial resources to earn higher returns. The hotel stakeholders may consciously monitor the external environmental factors to optimize its favorable effect on the hotel's performance and to mitigate its impossible negative consequences to the sustainability of business operations.

Lastly, although sustainable best practices and external environmental factors are determinants of hotel performance, the stakeholders of the hotel may continuously conduct evaluation and research studies to identify other relevant factors that will further develop the hotel management and its performance.

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